

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING IN VILLUPURAM DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study is separated into two main sections for easier comprehension and reading. The study describes the idea of consumer behavior in online purchasing in the first section. The second section reveals the history of the study that explains online shopping. We used a descriptive research design for this investigation. The research strategy was selected in order to maximize the reliability of the data collected. An approximate sample size of 80 respondents was used by the study's researcher. A sampling survey was used to gather primary data. The information was gathered from 80 respondents in the Villupuram area who were chosen among internet buyers. Based on the study it is concluded that online buyer in the Villupuram District are generally more satisfied with online shopping than they are with visiting physical businesses. The study found that small of amount of population is uninformed of internet shopping and doesn't utilize it, despite the fact that the majority of people are familiar with it.

Keywords: Buying Behaviour, Online Purchases, Online Shopping and Purchase Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

This study is separated into two main sections for easier comprehension and reading. The study describes the idea of consumer behavior in online purchasing in the first section. The paper then reveals the history of the study that explains online shopping. In India, the usage of the Internet as a source of information and for business is expanding quickly. According to estimates, the Indian e-commerce business would be worth \$99 billion by 2024. Internet use by many businesses is now commonplace for carrying out business operations and exchanging information with clients and partners. The internet provides direct connections with clients and vendors and streamlines business dealings, procedures, and information flow, among other things. It gives businesses access to low-cost but high-end tools for marketing,

accepting and processing orders, spreading their ideologies, and corresponding with clients globally.

Throughout the last two decades, the internet has expanded quickly, and a global information technology-driven digital economy has also been growing. Following the long-term development of the internet, which saw a sharp increase in web users and high-speed internet connections, as well as the creation and deployment of new technology for web development, this allowed businesses to better market their products and services online. The ability to communicate with someone who is physically on the other side of the world, send emails whenever they want, search for information, play games with others, and even make purchases online all make the internet a vital part of our everyday lives. As a method of making purchases of goods and services, online shopping is now generally accepted. In the world of the Internet, it has grown in popularity (Bourlakis et al., 2008). Nonetheless, some customers still feel uneasy making internet purchases. For instance, a lack of trust appears to be the main barrier to internet shopping for customers. Also, before making a purchase, shoppers could feel the urge to examine and handle the products, as well as meet friends and acquire additional feedback. Such elements might negatively affect a consumer's decision to shop online.

Many people prefer internet purchasing to traditional retail, which is why it is becoming more prevalent in daily life. People can pick up the products they want by using the internet for easy and convenient online shopping. To complete their purchases, customers simply need to click the pointer. Internet shopping simplifies both the act of shopping and daily life. Several factors have contributed to consumers moving their purchasing habits to online retail stores. One of the main advantages of internet buying is the ability to compare your goods with similar products that are available at a lower price and/or higher quality. Online shopping is the ordering and delivery of brand-new and conventional sale goods and services to the customer using electronic means. It makes it easier to get quick information about banking services and goods. The main advantages for clients include mobile and internet shopping from anyplace. Also, it has made it easier to utilize secured credit and debit cards, internet banking, and cash on delivery.

Online shopping has altered how people shop, and it has quickly become a global phenomenon. The goal of many businesses embracing online shopping was to save marketing expenses, which would force them to lower the price of their products in order to compete in

extremely cutthroat marketplaces. Businesses also utilize the Internet to connect, distribute, and deliver information and goods. Customers utilize the internet in a variety of ways, including to compare product features, costs, warranties, and delivery options in addition to making purchases. Numerous experts are optimistic about the future of the online marketing industry. Scholars continue to use a variety of perspectives to explain how e-consumers behave as retailing develops. A lot of research makes assumptions about consumer behavior based on traditional models before examining the efficacy of e-marketing.

In recent years, online purchasing has grown in importance. Many favor online purchasing over traditional retail because of their hectic schedules. Although there have been numerous studies in this field, the current study focuses on consumer patterns and behavior in order to comprehend how consumers' attitudes towards online shopping are changing and what changes are required for online shopping platforms in order to help them better understand the wants and needs of consumers. Yet, there are possible concerns associated with online buying for the consumers, including payment security and customer support. Because of the advancements in internet technology, online payments are now a common option to make purchases through the web. Consumptive efficiency is increased by online payments, but internet security is decreased by their virtual nature. Another approach to prevent online consumer buying is after service. Unlike traditional retail, there is a risk for the client that some after-service needs to be done face-to-face, particularly with some difficult goods.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Huseynov and Yildirim (2014) stressed that the lack of in-person connection frequently poses the biggest challenge to online retail sales, followed by concerns about the confidentiality of personal data and the security of online financial transactions.

K. Balakrishna, S. Srinivas Rao, and S. Manoj's 2016 article, online purchasing would dominate the market in the years to come. People prefer internet purchases because they are happy with them and there is good informal feedback. Online purchases are approached with a great degree of attentiveness. The quality and installation prior to delivery is the one area where purchases fall short.

Madasu Bhaskar Rao and M Mallika Rao (2018) identify the factors that influence consumer purchase behavior in online retail settings. The results of the exploratory factor analysis identified several characteristics, including ease of use and comfort, security, utility,

and time sufficiency, as well as drawing coordination's and criticism, as the predictors of female customers' online purchase behavior.

Dr. K. Nagendra Abu, Girisha M. C., and Veda Murthy M. B. (2020) The invention of the internet gave consumers a whole new experience in terms of acquiring information, comparing goods or pricing, and having the option of making purchases online. As a result, online consumer behavior is a crucial consideration for marketers. Marketers must comprehend how, where, and why consumers behave online in order to forecast their online behavior. In order to investigate which internet channels consumers use at each stage of the purchasing decision process, this study analyses studies conducted by various researchers (BDP).

Pawan Kumar and Kanchan (2017) conducted research. After analyzing the data, the researchers came to the conclusion that students are the ones that shop online the most. Customers consider a number of aspects before doing any online buying, including product quality, delivery speed, in-person product inspection, return policies, etc. So, in order to succeed and keep clients, internet businesses must consider those criteria.

Priyabrata Roy and Dhananjay Datta (2022) Institute of Chartered Analyst of India Vol. 9 (P) 358 has set objectives to investigate consumer buying behavior of west Tripura district consumers towards online and offline, to identify the major factors that impact consumer buying behavior. They've employed resources like primary and secondary data. They have come to the conclusion that this research study has provided precise information about customer purchasing behavior regarding online shopping, consumer preference, etc., which will be an important contributor for retailers in the future

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In general, a research problem is any challenge that a researcher encounters while working on a theoretical or practical project and for which they are looking for a solution. For networking, communication, and business, online platforms like Flipkart, Amazon, irctc.in, and Myntra have become quite popular. On websites for internet shopping, people can spend hours looking for specific things. The way that consumers shop online today, including the websites they visit and the products they buy, is a topic on which sellers are now more active. We chose this research topic, "A Study on Consumer Behavior Toward Online Shopping in Villupuram District," due to the rising numbers of online shoppers from sites

like Amazon, Flipkart, and Myntra, in order to seek for an increasing trend of online shopping in Villupuram District.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A study design outlines the steps for gathering and interpreting the data required to complete the research objectives (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). We used a descriptive research design for this investigation. The research strategy was selected in order to maximize the reliability of the data collected. An approximate sample size of 80 respondents was used by the study's researcher. A sampling survey was used to gather primary data. The information was gathered from 80 respondents in the Villupuram area who were chosen among internet buyers. It was suggested to use the survey method to gather data. The data are sampled using a non-probability sampling technique. The researcher's convenience will determine the sampling unit choice. The gathered information was collated, examined, and data analysis was done for the various levels of associations and interactions.

Objective of the study

The following study objectives were set in response to the research gaps found in the thorough literature assessment and while taking into account the significance of online buyer characteristics and their relationship to online shopping performance:

Primary Objectives:

- To examine how Villupuram district consumers behave when shopping online.

Secondary Objectives:

- To understand the online buyer's demographic trends.
- To evaluate the customer reference for online shopping
- To determine an online buyer's shopping experience.

Hypothesis

- ❖ Ho: There is no significant difference between the Consumer Behavior with respect to their Demographic Variable.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table No.1 Demographic Characteristics of online Consumers.

S. No	Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
	Age Group		
1	18 - 30 Years	58	72.5
2	31-40Years	10	12.5
3	41 - 50Years	7	8.75
4	50 Above	5	6.25
	Education Qualification		
5	High School	12	15
6	Diploma	13	16.25
7	Bachelor's Degree	46	57.5
8	Master Degree	09	11.25
	Area of living		
9	Villupuram (Township)	20	25
10	Tindivanam	20	25
11	Vikkiravandi	20	25
12	Gingee	20	25
	Amount to spend online Purchasing		
13	Less than 1000	23	28.75
14	1000 – 5000	29	36.25
15	5000 - 10,000	13	16.25
16	10,000 - 20,000	8	10
18	More than 20,000	7	8.75

The table 1 explains the demographic factors of the respondents. Out of 80 Online buying consumer 72.5 per cent belong to the age group 18 to 30 years of age, 12.5 per cent of the respondent belong to the age group from 31 to 40 years of age, 8.75 percentage of the respondent belong to the age group from 41 to 50 and the remaining 6.25 per cent of the respondents belong to the age group of above 50 years. The education wise classification of the Online buying consumer. In that 57.5 per cent have studied bachelor degree, 16.25 per

cent have studied diploma, 15 per cent have high school and the remaining 11.25 per cent is post graduates' level qualifications. The Online buying consumer a 25 per cent live in those areas Villupuram township, Tindivanam, Vikkiravandi and Gingee. The online buying consumer's 36.25 per cent of respondents to spent the amount of online purchasing Rs.1000 to 5000, 28.75 per cent of respondents to spent the amount of online purchasing Less than 1000, 16.25 per cent of respondents to spent the amount of online purchasing Rs. 5,000 to 10,000, 10 percent of respondents to spent the amount of online purchasing Rs. 10,000 to 20,000 and the remaining 8.75 per cent of respondents to spent the amount of online purchasing More than 20,000.

Table No.2 Opinion of Online Consumers Behavior.

Statements	Mean	Std.Dev
Shopping on internet saves times.	4.7252	0.78753
It is great advantage to be able to shop at any time of the day.	4.2684	0.75563
I prefer traditional/conventional shopping to online shopping.	3.1018	0.62189
Online shopping is risky.	3.8425	0.67658
Online shopping will eventually supersede traditional shopping.	4.1423	0.70760
A long time is required for the delivery of products and services.	3.0861	0.63229
Selection of goods available on the internet is very broad.	3.8295	0.65435
The description of products shown on the website are very accurate.	4.2243	0.72403
The information given about the product on the site is sufficient.	3.9198	0.69343
Online shopping is a secure as traditional shopping.	3.7860	0.68519
While shopping online I hesitate to give my credit card no.	3.8901	0.61054
Internet reduces the monetary cost of traditional shopping.	3.8622	0.64169
Necessity of having a bank account or credit card creates difficulty.	3.9301	0.70145
I prefer cash on delivery than payment via credit/debit card.	4.0347	0.73244

Table no - 2, illustrates the statement of online shopping consumer behavior. Factors were measured with fifteen statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard

deviation values were calculated. From the mean values it is noted shopping on internet saves time (4.72), It is great advantage to be able to shop at any time of the day (4.3), The description of products shown on the websites are very accurate (4.22), Online shopping will eventually supersede traditional shopping (4.14), I prefer cash on delivery than payment via credit/debit card (4.03), necessity of having a bank account or credit card creates difficulty (3.93), The information given about the product on the site is sufficient (3.91), While shopping online I hesitate to give my credit card no (3.9), Internet reduces the monetary cost of traditional shopping (3.86), Online shopping is risky (3.84), Selection of goods available on the internet is very broad (3.82), Online shopping is a secure as traditional shopping(3.8), I prefer traditional/conventional shopping to online shopping (3.1) and A long time is required for the delivery of products and services (3.08)

Table:3. ANOVA – Online consumer behavior with respect their Age.

AGE GROUP		N	Mean	Std. Dev	F	Sig.
ONLINE CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR	18 -30 Years	58	4.03	0.63	0.486	0.693
	31 – 40 Years	10	4.01	0.73		
	41 – 50 Years	5	3.85	0.62		
	51 Above	7	3.91	0.76		

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Online consumers’behaviour with respect their age.

As far as online consumer behavior is concerned, the significant value in the ANOVA result indicated at 5 % level of significance with the ‘significant value of 0.693 there is no significant difference in the mean value among their age and behavior. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table:4. ANOVA – Online Consumers behavior with respect their Education.

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION		N	Mean	Std. Dev	F	Sig.
ONLINE CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR	High schooling	12	3.85	0.67	1.035	0.377
	Diploma	13	4.10	0.76		
	Bachelor's degree	46	4.23	0.68		
	Master degree	9	3.73	0.78		

As far as consumer' behavior is concerned, the significant value in the ANOVA result indicated at 5 % level of significance with the 'significant value of 0.377 there is no significant difference in the mean value among their education and behavior. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table:5. ANNOVA – Online consumer behavior with respect their Area of Living.

AREA OF LIVING		N	Mean	Std. Dev	F	Sig.
ONLINE CONSUMER BEHAVIOR	Villupuram	20	4.02	0.73	0.012	0.968
	Tindivanam	20	3.98	0.71		
	Vikkiravandi	20	3.86	0.69		
	Gingee	20	4.10	0.74		

As far as consumers' behavior is concerned, the significant value in the ANNOVA result indicated at 5 % level of significance with the 'significant value of 0.968, there is no

significant difference in the mean value among their area of living and behavior. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table:6. Online Consumer behavior with respect their Amount to spend online Purchasing.

Amount to spend online Purchasing		N	Mean	Std. Dev	F	Sig.	Scheffe - Post Hoc
ONLINE CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR	Less than 1000	23	3.81	0.72	4.781	0.000	6vs1vs3vs 4vs2vs5
	1000-5000	29	4.28	0.83			
	5000-10000	13	4.00	0.70			
	10000-20000	8	3.84	0.57			
	More than 20000	7	3.80	0.50			

As far as consumers behavior is concerned, ANOVA showed a significant result ($F=4.781$; $p=0.001$), indicated at 5 % level of significance. This means that the consumer differ significantly with respect to their Amount to spend online purchasing towards consumer behavior. Hence the null hypothesis has been rejected. In order to check the most influencing group, scheffe post hoc comparison test was performed and the results show that the consumer' who are spend the amount of Rs.1000 to 5000 (mean=4.28; SD=0.83) significantly differ from others. That is, the consumer who are spend the amount of Rs.1000 to 5000 get more online consumer behavior compared to the consumer who are others.

VI. FINDINGS

- Majority of consumer 72.5 per cent belong to the age group 18 to 30 years of age and 12.5 per cent of the respondent belong to the age group from 31 to 40 years.

- Majority of consumer 57.5 per cent have studied bachelor's degree and 16.25 per cent have studied diploma.
- Majority of consumer 8.4 per cent live in the rural area and the remaining 21.6 per cent live in the urban area.
- Majority of consumers 36.25 per cent are spending Rs.1000 to 5000, 28.75 per cent are spending less than 1000, 16.25 per cent are spending Rs.5000 to 10,000, 10 per cent are spending Rs.10,000 to 20,000 and remaining 8.75 per cent are spending more than 20,000.
- The statement "the statement of online shopping consumer behavior are satisfactory" has common consent with mean value 4.72 and with standard deviation 0.79. Which means the is Shopping on internet saves times are satisfactory.
- There is no significant difference in the mean value among their age and Consumer behavior.
- There is no significant difference in the mean value among their education and Consumer behavior.
- There is no significant difference in the mean value among their area of living and Consumer behavior.
- The online buyer differ significantly with respect to their amount to spend online purchasing towards Consumer behavior. That is, consumer who are spend the amount Rs.1000 to 5000 get more Consumer behavior compared to the consumer who are spend the other amount.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the study it is concluded that online buyer in the Villupuram District are generally more satisfied with online shopping than they are with visiting physical businesses. The study found that small of amount of population is uninformed of internet shopping and doesn't utilize it, despite the fact that the majority of people are familiar with it. Despite the fact that most individuals are happy with their online shopping experiences, there are still a few issues to be resolved, such as poor product quality and delivery delays. The required efforts should be taken by online marketplaces to fix them. We also realized the importance of marketing methods in promoting online buying. Internet shopping has emerged as a blessing for all types of customers and has something to offer everyone, despite the fact that it is extremely handy, time-saving, and without a doubt, a cost-saving activity since one need not leave his or her home to conduct

business. Consumers are receiving far greater discounts, a wider selection of products, and - most importantly - direct user evaluations on apps and YouTube, so when we add together all of these factors, we can say that individuals in the Villupuram district shop online quite regularly.

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